

Background Data Preparation for Spatially Explicit Potential Vegetation Modelling in the CLIMANATRES Project to Support Sustainable Ecological Restorations in the Face of Climate Change

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Abstract: Ecological restoration is gaining prominence in nature conservation, particularly under the European Union's Nature Restoration Regulation, which emphasizes the need to integrate climate resilience into restoration planning. The CLIMANATRES project (Climate-proofing ecological restoration plans in the Middle and Lower Danube Region) addresses this demand by developing climate-resilient modeling tools across the Danube lowlands and adjacent mid-elevation mountains (<500 m a.s.l.). This study establishes a consistent climatic background variable set for potential natural vegetation (PNV) models that assess habitat survival under present and future climate conditions. We calculated bioclimatic variables based on the high-resolution (30 arc-sec, ≈ 1 km) CHELSA climate data for a reference period (1981–2010) and two future periods (2041–2070, 2071–2100) under two emission scenarios (SSP3-7.0, SSP5-8.5) and five global climate models. Nineteen bioclimatic variables were calculated following an ecologically refined protocol that fixes climate periods (e.g., wettest quarter) identified from the reference period to ensure comparability and ecological relevance under shifting seasonal patterns. The resulting high-resolution surfaces were integrated into the CLIMANATRES WebGIS platform to visualize spatial and temporal trends. This refined climatic dataset balances technical feasibility and ecological interpretability, providing a robust foundation for modeling vegetation-climate relationships and supporting climate-resilient ecological restoration planning across Middle and Lower Danube Region.

Keywords: ecological restoration; climate resilience; Potential natural vegetation (PNV); models; bioclimatic variables; CLIMANATRES project.

1 Introduction

Ecological restoration has emerged as a chief focus of nature conservation activities and is expected to remain so, thanks to the recently approved Nature Restoration Regulation (Nature Restoration Regulation, 2024). As the regulation also underlines, climate change is a major challenge in ecological restoration planning. CLIMANATRES (full title: Climate-proofing ecological restoration plans in the Middle and Lower Danube Region) is a Danube Interreg Programme project aiming at providing outputs that support climate-resilient ecological restoration planning across the biogeographically connected lowlands and medium mountains of the Middle and Lower Danube under ongoing climate change.

The CLIMANATRES project region covers lowlands and medium mountain territories of Bulgaria, Croatia, Hungary, Romania, Serbia, and Slovenia. This was complemented with the Po Valley in Italy to form the study area of the current research (Figure 1), as our preliminary analyses on climate analogy of the Po Valley revealed climatic similarity with the climate of the CLIMANATRES project region.

Potential natural vegetation modelling is a powerful tool in assessing abiotic requirements of natural vegetation types, habitats and eventually that of climate change impact on them (Somodi et al. 2021). Therefore, we aim to use

spatially explicit potential natural vegetation models in the frame of CLIMANATRES to assess habitat survival probability under current and future climate conditions.

Our study aims to lay the groundwork of establishing a climatic background variable set that is capable to serve the CLIMANATRES project incorporating the climatically analogous areas of Italy.

Figure 1. Map of the study area. The CLIMANATRES project region and the Po valley are highlighted by blue and green boundaries, respectively. The study area is not only a biogeographically and geomorphologically coherent area, but also shares possible ties regarding the spread of climate analogies between the current and future's climates of this region.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Background variables of potential vegetation models

We downloaded monthly values for mean, minimum, and maximum temperature and total precipitation from CHELSA database at 30 arc-sec (≈ 1 km) resolution for the reference period (1981–2010) and two future periods (2041–70, 2071–2100) (Karger et al. 2017). For the future periods, the 2×5 combination of two scenarios (SSP3-7.0, SSP5-8.5) and five global climate models (GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, UKESM1-0-LL) were used to measure and visualize model-driven uncertainty of both the bioclimatic variables and the potential vegetation models relying on them.

2.2 Calculation of bioclimatic variables

Since the focus of the modelling in CLIMANATRES is on (semi-)natural habitats, climate is represented in the models through the bioclimatic variables (Nix 1986, Busby 1991) as in (Somodi et al. 2017, Somodi et al. 2024). Names of the 19 bioclimatic variables describing temperature and precipitation-related climatic features relevant for ecological studies are listed by Karger et al. (2017). Bioclimatic variables are widely employed in models studying the distribution of species or vegetation types (Porfirio et al. 2014). There are several freely available databases that contain already calculated bioclimatic variables, e.g., WorldClim (Fick and Hijmans 2017), CHELSA (Karger et al. 2017), CliMond (Kriticos et al. 2012) and MERRAclim (Vega et al. 2017). However, there are multiple ways how bioclimatic variables can be calculated (Bede-Fazekas and Somodi 2020, Pinilla-Buitrago and Osorio-

Olvera 2026), and different calculation methods can result in heterogeneous model predictions (Bede-Fazekas and Somodi 2020). Prediction heterogeneity is especially pronounced if a larger region with heterogeneous specific climate periods (e.g., wettest quarter of the year), such as our study area, is involved in a research (Bede-Fazekas and Somodi 2024). Therefore, while bioclimatic variables are readily available at the CHELSA database, we opt to recalculate them following an alternative protocol detailed below: (1) in the case of maximum/minimum temperature of warmest/coldest month (BCV5 and BCV6, respectively), we calculated the maximum/minimum temperature of the month that has the highest/lowest mean temperature, (2) for each location, specific climate periods were identified once in the reference period (i.e., near past) and used consequently in the future periods (the specific climate periods were not recalculated for the future periods). Hence, the future bioclimatic variables (e.g., the temperature of the wettest month) describe the future climate (e.g., temperature) of the specific climate period (e.g., wettest quarter) determined in the reference period. This fixing of the specific climate period is needed because some of these periods can remarkably shift within the year (e.g., the wettest quarter of Osijek, Croatia is predicted to shift from May-June-July to October-November-December or November-December-January by the end of the 21st century according to the UKESM1-0-LL global climate model, Figure 2). While this calculation method differs from the one applied in the freely available databases, it

enhances the ecological relevance of the bioclimatic variables and improves model transferability (Bede-Fazekas and Somodi 2020).

3 Results

In the frame of the project, the 19 bioclimatic variables calculated became part of the WebGIS platform developed for the CLIMANATRES project and available online: <https://climanatres.geof.hr/gis>.

The background data preparation resulted in 19 bioclimatic variables for the reference period and 2x2x5 combinations of future periods, scenarios and global climate models, respectively. Our calculations resulted in fine resolution (~1 km, visually continuous) surface of each of the 19 bioclimatic variables. Due to the large number of future combinations, each bioclimatic variable was visualized in a nested framework using a common color scale to enhance comparability between the global climate models. The composite figures were arranged to assist the interpretation of temporal change and the interscenario variability. Here we provide two examples from the set of figures, both showing bioclimatic variables according to the UKESM1-0-LL global climate model. The temperature of the wettest quarter (BCV8) is a combined variable (i.e., temperature and precipitation data are needed for its calculation) dependent on a specific climate period, and it shows abrupt changes along spatial gradients where the wettest quarter of the year changes in the reference period (Figure 3). However, some of the bioclimatic variables, such

Figure 2. Wettest quarter of the year in the reference period (1981-2010) and two future periods (2041-70, 2071-2100) according to the SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios and the UKESM1-0-LL global climate model. Months are abbreviated with their initials.

as the annual precipitation (BCV12) show well-known spatial patterns following the topography continuously (Figure 4).

4 Discussion

Climate variables are available from various databases as listed in Table 1. Based on the thorough understanding of the details of the climate databases, we concluded that both WorldClim and Chelsa databases are optimal choices as input data sources for climatic data in the subsequent analysis. In favor of the Chelsa database, we could highlight that its future data are already bias-corrected and its elaborated downscaling method for precipitation variables. The precipitation downscaling accounted for elevation-driven orographic processes using corrections for wind exposure, valley exposition, and boundary layer effects (Karger et al. 2017).

The 19 climatic variables constitute a starting variable set for modelling in CLIMANATRES and potentially beyond for other efforts. The dataset enables relating the climate change scenarios with the potential vegetation types, as a practical tool for systematic conservation planning (Margules and Pressey 2000), improving our confidence in cost-efficiency considered in habitat restoration efforts (Strassburg et al. 2019). However, the availability of the 19 BCVs does not mean that all of these can be simultaneously used in models. Variable selection based on pairwise correlations and multicollinearity is necessary to conduct in order to select candidate variables for modelling (Dormann et al. 2013).

The ~1 km resolution represents a compromise between technical factors and interpretability. Dynamic downscaling (by regional climate models) reaches ~10 km resolution (such as in MedCORDEX or EuroCORDEX, Jacob et al. 2014, Ruti et al. 2016). Climate change impact

assessments, however, require resolution closer to landscape dynamics, including ecological assessments (e.g., Somodi et al. 2017, Bede-Fazekas and Somodi 2020). While ecological applications would prefer finer resolution, as also identified in a stakeholder survey within CLIMANATRES (Lanšćák and Basrek 2026), statistical downscaling limits hinder going beyond ~1 km resolution yet. Thus, the currently calculated variables offer an acceptable compromise between technical constraints and application needs.

5 Conclusions

Preparation of climate-related background variables resulted in a rich database for the CLIMANATRES project. They provide an excellent starting point to reflect the climatic requirements of vegetation.

However, this background variable set also provides a rich source of potential background variables for other efforts in the region. They can serve educational purposes, statistical analyses, and feed into predictive models of other ecological phenomena, thus proliferating the impact of the CLIMANATRES project.

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Table 1. Spatial (coverage, resolution) and temporal (coverage, resolution) attributes of the potential databases along with the availability of global and regional climate models and scenarios. Notations are as follows: green OK – optimal, yellow tilde – suboptimal, red cross – problematic or unusable.

Climate database	File format	Coordinate reference system	Spatial coverage	Spatial resolution	Temporal coverage	Temporal resolution	Global or regional climate models	Scenarios	Climate variables
WorldClim	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Climond	~	OK	OK	×	~	OK	×	×	OK
Chelsa	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Chelsa-EUR11	~	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	~	×
MERRAclim	OK	OK	OK	~	×	OK	×	×	~
TerraClimate	~	OK	OK	~	×	OK	OK	×	OK
E-OBS	~	OK	OK	OK	×	~	×	×	OK
Euro-Cordex	~	×	OK	×	OK	~	OK	~	OK

Figure 3. Temperature of the wettest quarter (BCV8) in the reference period (1981–2010) and two future periods (2041–70, 2071–2100) according to the SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios and the UKESM1-0-LL global climate model.

Figure 4. Annual precipitation (BCV12) in the reference period (1981–2010) and two future periods (2041–70, 2071–2100) according to the SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios and the UKESM1-0-LL global climate model.

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